

UKBOL Standard Operating Procedure: Submitting specimen data to BOLD systems v.5

Version 1, March 2026

Select all of the data from cell A2 by selecting cell A2 and clicking **ctrl + shift + down arrow** and **ctrl + shift + right arrow**.

Copy **ctrl + c** and paste **ctrl + v** all of the data to a new empty spreadsheet.

Once pasted click on the (ctrl) button in the right bottom corner.

And select the button under 'Paste values' > '123' on the clipboard.

The screenshot shows an Excel spreadsheet with columns for specimen metadata. A context menu is open over the spreadsheet, showing the 'Paste' options. The 'Paste Values' option is selected, and its sub-menu is visible, with the '123' button highlighted. The spreadsheet data includes columns for SAMPLEID, FIELDID, MUSEUM, COLLECTOR, INST, FUNDING, PHYLUM, CLASS, ORDER, FAMILY, SUBFAMIL, TRIBE, GENUS, SPECIES, SUBSPECI, IDENTIFIE, IDENTIFIC, TAXONOM, SEX, and RE.

This pastes the cell data without the underlying excel formulas and it should then look like this:

The screenshot shows the same Excel spreadsheet as above, but the underlying formulas have been removed. The data is now plain text. The '123' button in the 'Paste Values' dropdown menu is still visible, indicating that the data has been pasted as values.

Double check that none of the data is corrupted, and that all of the required columns are filled:

- **Sample ID**
- **Field ID** and/or **Museum ID**
- **Institution storing**
- **Phylum** from Taxonomic ranks
- **Country / Ocean**

Save it to a bold uploads folder under the name [batchnumber]_processing_BOLD.

Now log into your BOLD account and click on 'projects' dropdown on the left panel and then 'View All Projects'.

Once you are in 'My Projects' click on 'DEFRA'.

Unselect All

My Projects

General Projects 15 Projects, 20158 Specimens

Code	Title	Public	Specimens	Species	Species with Sequences Markers [stats]	Sequences Markers [stats]	Project Tags
<input type="checkbox"/> GENPR	Private holding project for various ongoing studies		162	36	COI-5P[0]	COI-5P[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> UKBOL	UK Barcoding		25194	5853	COI-5P[2433], ITS2[1116], rbcL[1445], matK[1345], ITS[0], 12S[0], ITS1[0]	COI-5P[7399], ITS2[2588], rbcL[4516], matK[3263], ITS[0], 12S[0], ITS1[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> ANBIO	Ainsdale BioBlitz		625	311	COI-5P[244]	COI-5P[479]	
<input type="checkbox"/> ASCEN	Expanding genetic biomonitoring on Ascension Island		0	0	COI-5P[0], 12S[0]	COI-5P[0], 12S[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> BURE	Bure Marshes Bioblitz		378	281	COI-5P[142]	COI-5P[159]	
<input type="checkbox"/> DEFRA	UKBOL accelerated		0	0	COI-5P[0], ITS2[0], rbcL[0], matK[0], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	COI-5P[0], ITS2[0], rbcL[0], matK[0], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> FBUK	FreshBase: UK freshwater macroinvertebrate genomic reference collection		490	428	COI-5P[213]	COI-5P[254]	
<input type="checkbox"/> HELEN	St Helena Barcode Reference Library		81	65	COI-5P[45]	COI-5P[57]	
<input type="checkbox"/> MISSM	Mission Malaise		8550	0	COI-5P[0]	COI-5P[3336]	

javascriptmergeProjects();

And then click on the 'Uploads' dropdown on the left panel and click on 'Specimen Data'.

BOLDSYSTEMS

Sophia K Reinisch

Back to Main Console

Project DEFRA

View All Records

Project Options

Publication

Uploads

- Specimen Data
- Specimen Images

Downloads

Sequence Analysis

Aggregate Data

Project & Dataset Search

Code Record Search

Project - DEFRA UKBOL accelerated

Activity Report

Specimens	Sequences	Descriptors	Data Summary
0 Specimens	0 Sequences	<p>Codes: DEFRA</p> <p>Markers: COI-5P, ITS2, rbcL, matK, ITS, ITS1</p> <p>Title: UKBOL accelerated</p> <p>Description: UKBOL accelerated – automation pipeline development and validation</p> <p>Container: UKBOL</p> <p>Campaign: General Projects</p> <p>Bounding Box Coordinates: N/A</p> <p> This project has been released publicly.</p>	<p>BINS: 0</p> <p>Countries (Top 5):</p>
<p> GPS: 0 / 0</p> <p> Country: 0 / 0</p> <p> Images: 0 / 0</p> <p> Barcode Compliant: 0 / 0</p>			

Then you will be on submission page and you click on 'Initiate Batch Submission'.

B Specimen Data Submission

Batch Submission

Specimen records can be submitted one at a time with the form below or through the batch submission process using a spreadsheet submission package. Additional information regarding the two approaches to submitting records is available in the [BOLD documentation](#).

Initiate Batch Submission

Specimen Identifiers

Sample ID:

Field ID:
(Field ID or Museum ID must be entered)

Museum ID:

Collection Code:

Institution Storing:
To choose the institution storing, type in the name and select it from the drop-down list of matches.

javascript:void(0)

Make sure 'ADD NEW Records' is selected and click on 'Next'.

B Specimen Data Batch Submission

Please select the type of submission you would like to complete from one of the following:

ADD NEW Records: Submit new records to a project.

UPDATE Existing Records: Update some or all fields on records that have been previously submitted to BOLD.

Note: To update current records and submit new records, you must submit two independent submissions. *For more information, please visit our [Resources](#) section.*

Next **Cancel**

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Click on 'Choose File' and upload your specimen metadata spreadsheet.

Instructions for New Submissions NEW

BOLD supports the upload of multiple specimen records in a spreadsheet format. The BOLD5 single or multi-page spreadsheet can be downloaded below:

[BOLD5 BCDM Single-Page Submission Template](#)
[BOLD5 BCDM Multi-Page Submission Template](#)

The BOLD5 spreadsheet submission templates contain all the fields supported by BOLD5's BCDM standards and fields previously supported by BOLDv2.5, BOLDv3.1, and BOLDv4. Further information on BOLD5 fields can be found [here](#).

File Submission

Excel Spreadsheet: No file chosen

Priority Level: High Priority
Reserved for when immediate processing is required (i.e. publication pending). High priority submissions usually take 1-3 business days to process, depending on the length of the high priority queue.

Colleagues (CC):
Enter the email addresses of colleagues you would like to copy (CC) on your submission, separated by commas.

Description:
For Updates, please list the sheets that should be updated (Voucher, Taxonomy, Specimen Details and/or Collection Data).

Once the sheet is uploaded, tick 'High Priority', fill in the 'Colleagues (CC):' with **"b.price@nhm.ac.uk, sophia.reinisch2@nhm.ac.uk"** and fill the description with your Batch Number and any other relevant information. Then click on **Submit**.

Specimen Data Batch Submission | BOLDSYSTEMS - Work - Microsoft Edge

https://bench.boldsystems.org/index.php/MAS_DataCollection_FileSub?subtype=specimendatafile&pcode=DEFRA

[BOLD5 BCDM Single-Page Submission Template](#)
[BOLD5 BCDM Multi-Page Submission Template](#)

The BOLD5 spreadsheet submission templates contain all the fields supported by BOLD5's BCDM standards and fields previously supported by BOLDv2.5, BOLDv3.1, and BOLDv4. Further information on BOLD5 fields can be found [here](#).

File Submission

Excel Spreadsheet: [BATCH NUMBER]_processing_BOLD.xlsx

1 **Priority Level:** High Priority
Reserved for when immediate processing is required (i.e. publication pending). High priority submissions usually take 1-3 business days to process, depending on the length of the high priority queue.

2 **Colleagues (CC):**
Enter the email addresses of colleagues you would like to copy (CC) on your submission, separated by commas.

3 **Description:**
For Updates, please list the sheets that should be updated (Voucher, Taxonomy, Specimen Details and/or Collection Data).

4

You will probably get these errors, it is safe to ignore them and click with 'Submit with Errors'. IF you get any other errors there is something wrong with the spreadsheet or data that needs to be revised.

After submitting you will get email from the BOLD data team confirming your metadata upload, you may receive information regarding any issues resolved by them, or outstanding data issues you need to resolve.

In order to resolve any submission errors or inaccuracies you can edit the record on the BOLD website directly by clicking on 'Edit specimen' on the specimen page.

Otherwise you can also do a batch edit of submissions as outlined below:

Search your sample IDs in the 'Record Search' window in the BOLD project page.

Make sure to select 'Sample IDs' as Identifiers and fill in the sample IDs of the records you want to edit in the text box, then click Search Record.

For any multi-word searches, please use quotes to encapsulate each search term.

Taxonomy

Geography
Country/Province

Sequence Length
Marker Minimum Maximum

Tags

Depository

Extra Info

Collection Range
From: 02-Oct-2005 To: 25-Mar-2009

Region of Map List of Identifiers

Identifiers

Process IDs

GenBank Accession

Sample IDs

BIN URI (e.g. BOLD:AAA0965)

UK001-B01
UK001-C01

To search for multiple entries, place each on a separate line

Search within project [DEFRA]

Select all of the records and click on 'Data Spreadsheets'.

The interface shows a sidebar with 'Data Spreadsheets' highlighted. The main area displays summary statistics for 3 specimens and 13 sequences, including progress bars for GPS, Country, Images, Barcode Compliant, COI-5P, 16S, CYTB, COII, and COXIII. A donut chart shows the common genus 'Exotela' with three species: Exotela senecionis (1), Exotela arunci (1), and Exotela obscura (1). Below is a table of records with checkboxes for selection.

Selection	Identification	Specimen Page	Sequence Page	Extra Info	BIN	Record Flags	Legend	COI-SP
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Exotela senecionis	UK001-A01	DEFRA191-26			📍 2 0	*	356[0n]
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Exotela obscura	UK001-B01	DEFRA192-26			📍 2 0	*	653[0n]
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Exotela arunci	UK001-C01	DEFRA193-26			📍 2 0	*	653[0n]

Select the spreadsheet which contains the data that you would like to edit and download it.

Spreadsheet Download - Search: Sample IDs (3 records returned) (3 records selected)

The configuration screen shows 'Lab: Progress Report' selected. Below is a section for 'Specimen Data' with the following options:

- Vouchers
- Taxonomy
- Specimen Details
- Collection Data
- Custom Fields
- Tags

The 'Format' dropdown is set to 'Multi-Page'. A 'Download' button is located at the bottom right.

Open up the downloaded spreadsheet, edit any relevant columns / cells, and save it as an excel worksheet (.xlsx).

Sample ID	Collectors	Collection Date	Country/Ocean	State/Province	Region	Sector	Exact Site	Lat	Lon	Elev	Depth	Elevation Precision	Depth Precision	GPS Source	Coordinates
UK001-A01	J.T. Nowasko	20-Jun-1961	Poland				Spadowiec V	49.278	19.951						
UK001-B01	F. Groschke	23-Aug-1955	Germany				Neuffen, Wu	48.5	9.3						
UK001-C01	E.M. Hering	18-Feb-1953	Germany				Rostock, Mec	54	12						

Go back to the BOLD website, onto the relevant project folder, and click on 'Uploads' and 'Specimen Data'.

BOLD SYSTEMS

Sophia K Reinisch

Back to Main Console

Project DEFRA

View All Records

Project Options

Publication

Uploads

- Specimen Data**
- Specimen Images

Downloads

Sequence Analysis

Aggregate Data

Primers

Project & Dataset Search

Code Record Search

Project - DEFRA UKBOL accelerated

Specimens

1493 Specimens

GPS: 1361 / 1493

Country: 1493 / 1493

Images: 1493 / 1493

Barcode Compliant: 0 / 1493

Sequences

5463 Sequences

COI-5P: 1396/1493

16S: 564/1493

CYTB: 990/1493

12S: 390/1493

COII: 1080/1493

COXIII: 1043/1493

Descriptors

Codes: DEFRA

Markers: COI-5P, 16S, CYTB, ND4, 12S, COII, ND2, atp6, MT-NADH5, COXIII, ATP8, ND1, ND3, ND6, ND4L

Title: UKBOL accelerated

Description: UKBOL accelerated - automation pipeline development and validation

Container: UKBOL

Campaign: General Projects

Bounding Box Coordinates: N/A

Coordinates:

Public Release: This project has been released publicly.

Click on 'Initiate Batch Submission'.

Specimen Data Submission

Batch Submission

Specimen records can be submitted one at a time with the form below or through the batch submission process using a spreadsheet submission package. Additional information on the two approaches to submitting records is available in the [BOLD documentation](#).

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Specimen Identifiers

Sample ID:

Field ID:
(Field ID or Museum ID must be entered)

Museum ID:

Collection Code:

Institution Storing:
To choose the institution storing, type in the name and select it from the drop-down list of matches.

Specimen Taxonomy

Identifier:

Make sure to select 'UPDATE Existing Records' and then Next.

Specimen Data Batch Submission

Please select the type of submission you would like to complete from one of the following:

ADD NEW Records: Submit new records to a project.

UPDATE Existing Records: Update some or all fields on records that have been previously submitted to BOLD.

Note: To update current records and submit new records, you must submit two independent submissions. For more information, please visit our [Resources](#) section.

Next **Cancel**

Import the spreadsheet with the relevant edits, tick ‘High Priority’, fill in the ‘Colleagues (CC):’ with “b.price@nhm.ac.uk, sophia.reinisch2@nhm.ac.uk” and fill the description with your Batch Number and details on which metadata columns are updating. Then click on **Submit**.

Only records the user has specimen edit access to can be updated.

Please note that these updates will overwrite data on BOLD. To ensure that data is not inadvertently overwritten, please allow up to 2 weeks for BOLD staff to process new submissions/previous updates. Also note that blank cells will clear previously existing data.

After successfully submitting your data to BOLD, our data submission staff will be in contact if there are any apparent errors or queries regarding the submitted data or when the data has been successfully processed.

File Submission

Excel Spreadsheet:

No file chosen

Priority Level:

High Priority

Reserved for when immediate processing is required (i.e. publication pending). High priority submissions usually take 1-3 business days to process, depending on the length of the high priority queue.

Colleagues (CC):

b.price@nhm.ac.uk, sophia.reinisch2@nhm.ac.uk

Enter the email addresses of colleagues you would like to copy (CC) on your submission, separated by commas.

Description:

Batch 001 metadata update : Collection start date updated in Collection Data

For Updates, please list the sheets that should be updated (Voucher, Taxonomy, Specimen Details and/or Collection Data).